

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF MODERN LINGUISTICS AND
INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Annotation: Today, an important aspect of modern world linguistics is the absorption and interaction of scientific information that is inextricably linked with various fields of human activity. To provide students with thorough knowledge about the specific features of new directions in linguistics, such as ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, mathematical linguistics, computer linguistics, as a result of the interaction of linguistics with various scientific fields, and to boldly send young talents to these fields. must

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competence, didactics.

Today, in the process of teaching foreign languages in higher educational institutions, it is necessary to approach it as a system, to interpret the language and its units and phenomena on the basis of the laws of the system, to provide in-depth knowledge about the asymmetry of form and content, the functional versatility of the mother tongue, and to train theoretically mature linguists. It is necessary to clearly define the position of historical linguistics.

In the current era of globalization, researching innovative educational technologies and their pedagogical foundations, researching ways to effectively use modern interactive teaching methods in the educational process remains one of the urgent problems of today. The socio-pedagogical necessity of an innovative approach to education is measured by:

1. Scientific-technical development and socio-economic renewal of the continuous education system, in particular, improvement of the educational process in educational institutions using the study of advanced foreign experiences, innovative approaches in education and information technologies;
2. Creation and implementation of effective organizational forms and technologies of person-oriented education that serve to develop the level of education, intellectual potential, social activity, and creativity skills of students;
3. The need to develop the professional-innovative competence of the teacher in relation to mastering and implementing pedagogical innovations.

Technical means to improve the quality of education: audio-video, film materials, computers, video projector, slides, excerpts from works of art; they use

modern pedagogical technologies, especially interactive methods. Innovative educational technologies improve the quality of education, increase its effectiveness, establish mutual cooperation between the teacher, student and the team, achieve ideological and spiritual unity, strive for a single goal, each. It has great potential in creating the necessary conditions and environment for the realization of the learner's inner potential, manifestation as a person.

Currently, a lot of work is being done not only on teaching foreign languages, but also on finding new methods of teaching and teaching all subjects and testing them in practice. This is one of the most important problems that must be solved in order to improve the educational process today. If before, teaching a foreign language was considered to be the study of this language system, in the following years, the main aim of teaching was to develop students' foreign language speech. It should be said that these goals in learning a foreign language are not set by themselves or by other people or individuals, but are closely related to changes in the sciences of linguistics and psychology and the social development of society. For example: Let's take the audiolingual method. The emergence of this method was influenced by changes in linguistics, i.e. structural flow. It includes the following factors: - Teaching a foreign language must begin with teaching oral speech; - Language learning is carried out on the basis of various structures and speech patterns; - Exercises also require language-based exercises that require repetition of language material many times; - The selection of grammatical patterns and lexis should depend on the results of comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue. - Pronunciation requires a lot of attention. The main disadvantage of this method is the large number of mechanical exercises and the small number of actual speech exercises. The founders of this method are Methodist scientists Ch. Friz and R. Ladolar. For example: Ch. Friz says that the main content of the initial stage should be the study of structures. It is desirable that the formation of grammar skills should be based on this.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted education, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic

method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high. Currently, foreign languages are taught in schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher education institutions. There are innovative types of educational materials for those who want to have different levels of language knowledge. Perfect knowledge of a foreign language and obtaining a certain level also depends on the practical methods and qualifications of teachers. Information technologies and modern teaching methods the ability to use helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning is effective in this regard. Nowadays, innovations are increasing in every field.

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